

Validation of the MOOSE-Based Application Griffin with SEFOR Isothermal Experiments

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ABSTRACT

Griffin is a MOOSE-based deterministic neutron transport code that solves the linearized Boltzmann equation with multigroup energy discretization, and multiple angular schemes, using finite element methods on unstructured meshes with both continuous and discontinuous Galerkin formulations. In this work, we benchmark Griffin on the SEFOR cores I-E and I-I using zero-power isothermal tests of Doppler and net thermal reactivity feedback. Monte Carlo reference models were developed with Serpent and Shift for code-to-code verifications. 3-D fully heterogeneous meshes of cores I-E and I-I were generated directly via the MOOSE Reactor Mesh Module. The DFEM-SN solver in Griffin was used, and cross sections were supplied from MC²-3, converted to ISOXML, and used in microscopic form. ANL 33-energy groups structure was used in this analysis. To enable efficient large-scale simulations of the 33-group SN transport problem, we employed a split-mesh, distributed-memory workflow and CMFD acceleration. Results show good agreement among Griffin with the SEFOR measurements for both cores. The findings of this work demonstrate the feasibility and accuracy of a fully heterogeneous, deterministic Griffin modeling approach for predicting thermal reactivity feedback in SEFOR isothermal experiments.

Keywords: MOOSE, Griffin, SEFOR, Doppler effect, nuclear data

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 1960s, the Southwest Experimental Fast Oxide Reactor (SEFOR) was conceived to demonstrate that fast breeder reactors using mixed-oxide (MOX) fuel and liquid sodium coolant could be both economical and inherently safe. A key passive safety mechanism during unprotected transients is a negative fuel-temperature (Doppler) reactivity coefficient. Thus, there was a need to validate Doppler reactivity feedback predictions through whole-core experiments.

Backed by the U.S. Atomic Energy Commission, General Electric, and other partners, SEFOR was designed to provide direct experimental validation of Doppler and fuel expansion feedback in a realistic MOX-fueled [1-2], sodium-cooled fast core. SEFOR operated in Arkansas from 1969 to 1972 at a nominal 20 MWth, as a pool-type sodium-cooled fast reactor specifically tailored to probe Doppler reactivity at elevated temperatures. The program covered zero-power measurements, steady-state tests across power levels, and transient experiments. These campaigns produced datasets on reactivity worth, kinetics, and reactivity feedback under isothermal, steady state or dynamic conditions.

Under the DOE Nuclear Energy Advanced Modeling and Simulation (NEAMS) program, we conducted a preliminary validation of the MOOSE-based reactor physics application Griffin [3] which is a finite-element based neutron transport solver, using experimental data from the SEFOR reactor. Validation of Griffin against experimental benchmarks, such as SEFOR, is essential for establishing its predictive

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accuracy across diverse reactor systems and operating conditions. In this paper, we focus on SEFOR isothermal experiments for cores I-E and I-I. In these experiments, the sodium coolant was gradually heated from approximately 449.8 K to 677.6 K (350 °F to 760 °F) using trace heaters, and the resulting negative reactivity was tracked via reflector positioning.

2. SEFOR CORE DESIGN

The SEFOR core used mixed U-Pu oxide fuel in hexagonal assemblies and featured a segmented rod design with nickel end reflectors, depleted UO_2 insulation layers, and springs to accommodate axial expansion. SEFOR deployed variants such as higher-fissile “Guinea Pig” rods, B4C rods, and instrumented fuel rods with thermocouples in core I-I; a central DryWell channel housed the Fast Reactivity Excursion Device for transients. Two SEFOR core configurations were formed. The first configuration (SEFOR core I) used BeO tightener rods at the center of each fuel assembly, while in the second core configuration (core II), the BeO rods were replaced with stainless steel rods, resulting in a slightly harder neutron spectrum compared to core I. For core I, zero-power experiments were carried out in seven different core loadings, designated core I-A through I-I. The isothermal experiments modeled in this paper were conducted in core I-E and core I-I. Figure 1 shows the core loadings along with the standard designs of fuel assemblies and fuel rods.

Figure 1. SEFOR cores I-E and I-I, with standard fuel assembly and fuel rod designs [1,2].

3. GRIFFIN NEUTRONIC MODEL

To accurately represent SEFOR's heterogeneous core, several specialized mesh generators within the MOOSE Reactor Module [4] were employed, which streamlined the mesh-generation process. Cylindrical components such as fuel pins, insulators, wire wraps, and absorber pins were meshed using the "AdvancedConcentricCircleGenerator" mesh generator. The central tightener pin and its surrounding duct were modeled with the "HexagonConcentricCircleAdaptiveBoundaryMeshGenerator" mesh generator, which provides adaptive boundary meshing optimized for hexagonal lattice structures. Fuel assemblies, including their ducts and inter-assembly gaps, were then constructed using the "FlexiblePatternGenerator" mesh generator, which supports multiple assembly types. Representative meshes for the different assembly types for cores I-E and I-I are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Example of 2D mesh of fuel assemblies generated using MOOSE Reactor Modules for cores I-E and I-I.

The assemblies were packed into the full core layout using the "PatternedHexMeshGenerator" mesh generator. Peripheral regions (the downcomer, outer vessel, radial reflector, and radial shield) were then meshed and coupled to the core with the "PeripheralRingMeshGenerator" mesh generator. At this stage, the model comprised a two-dimensional mesh, as shown in Fig. 3. To construct the full three-dimensional reactor geometry, we used the "AdvancedExtruderGenerator" mesh generator to axially extrude the 2D core mesh to the prescribed height. This tool supports user-defined layer thicknesses and region remapping, enabling axial segments to be inserted, reordered, or redefined to capture SEFOR's complex axial heterogeneities. The resulting 3-D axial core mesh is shown in Fig. 4. To improve parallel performance, Griffin simulations were run with a split-mesh configuration. The mesh-splitting setup is defined in the Mesh block of the Griffin input, and the Griffin executable is used to generate the pre-split mesh.

The neutron transport equation was solved using Griffin's DFEM-SN solver with Gauss-Chebyshev angular quadrature. For the Multiphysics cases, the quadrature employed three polar angles and either four or six azimuthal angles. Angular fluxes were discretized with MONOMIAL, first-order finite-element shape functions, and the maximum scattering anisotropy order was set to 2. Although Griffin provides an embedded MC²-3 workflow for fast-reactor cross-section generation, it was not used here due to SEFOR's geometric complexities. Instead, multigroup cross sections produced by MC²-3 within the ARC [5] workflow were imported for the SEFOR analyses, and microscopic cross-sections with 33-group energy structure was employed. The binary MC²-3 output was converted to ISOXML format using Griffin utilities.

Figure 3. 2D radial mesh of Core I-E(left) and Core I-I (right) generated using MOOSE Reactor Module.

Figure 4. 3D axial mesh of Core I-E (left) and Core I-I (right) generated using MOOSE Reactor Module.

A detailed two-dimensional neutron transport analysis of the SEFOR I-E core was first performed and benchmarked against a reference solution of the identical 2D model and nuclear data library (ENDF/B-VII.1) using Serpent 2 Monte Carlo. This comparison confirmed the adequacy of the spatial discretization and the fidelity of the adopted multigroup cross sections. Given the core's pronounced heterogeneity, no radial symmetry or homogenization assumptions were applied; instead, a full-core 2D X–Y model was constructed. The model was evaluated under uniform isothermal conditions at 449.8 K, with vacuum boundary conditions radially and reflective boundaries axially. A 33-group cross-section set based on ENDF/B-VII.1, generated with MC2-3, was employed, and transport was solved using Griffin's DFEM–SN solver. Multiplication factors obtained under various angular discretizations—varying the number of scattering moments (NA), polar angles (NP), and azimuthal angles (NAzmthl)—are summarized in Table 1. Minor discrepancies were observed among the tested cases. The configuration NA=3, NP=3, NAzmthl=6 yielded the closest agreement with the Serpent 2 reference (for the same radial layout), with a discrepancy of approximately -7.63 pcm.

Table 1. Multiplication factor of 2D SEFOR core I-E with various angular discretization

NA	NP	NAzmthl	k-eff	Diff. (pcm)*
1	3	4	1.16398	-49.44
2	3	4	1.16485	38.40
3	3	4	1.16462	15.38
3	3	6	1.16439	-7.63
3	3	8	1.16462	15.08
3	6	4	1.16483	36.03

*Reference Serpent2: 1.16447 ± 0.00004

Building on the 2D model, we extended the analysis to a fully 3D core model in which axial heterogeneities were represented explicitly. This transition markedly increased mesh complexity and element counts. Mesh discretization statistics for cores I-E and I-I (including total degrees of freedom (DOFs), nodes, and elements) are summarized in Table 2. The core I-I configuration required roughly three times as many elements as I-E, with commensurate increases in DOFs and computational cost, resulting in a substantially higher memory footprint in Griffin.

Table 2. Discretization and mesh statistics for core I-E and core I-I

Parameters	Core I-E	Core I-I
Num of DOFs	4.189E+10	1.128E+11
Num of local DOFs	2.07E+07	5.81E+07
Mesh nodes total	2.36E+06	6.17E+06
Mesh nodes local	1.42E+03	3.82E+03
Mesh elements total	3.30E+06	8.90E+06
Mesh elements local	1.60E+03	4.58E+03

Three-dimensional transport simulations were performed with Griffin’s DFEM–SN solver using 3 scattering moments (NA), 3 polar angles (NP), 6 azimuthal angles (NAzmthl), and Coarse-Mesh Finite Difference (CMFD) acceleration to enhance computational efficiency. In Table 3, the Shift Monte Carlo code served as the reference configuration. Griffin-calculated multiplication factors at a uniform 449.8 °F, together with the corresponding Shift results for Core I-E, are summarized in Table 3. The 3D core geometries and material layouts were consistent between the two codes. The Griffin runs required approximately 7 hours on 2,016 CPU cores (84 nodes × 24 cores) and consumed about 16 TB of aggregate memory. When comparing nuclear data libraries, Griffin’s k-effective differed by roughly 125 pcm between ENDF/B-VII.0 and ENDF/B-VII.1, whereas Shift exhibited a much larger difference of about 423 pcm. The ENDF/B-VII.0 library used by Shift [6] (from SCALE 6.2) contains a known error in probability-table generation that disproportionately impacts fast-spectrum systems, explaining the larger discrepancy in the Shift results.

Table 3. Multiplication factor of 3D SEFOR core I-E with various angular discretization

Nuclear Library	Code	k_{eff}	Diff. (pcm)
ENDF/B-VII.0	Shift	1.01525 ± 0.00004	Ref.
	Griffin	1.01365	160
ENDF/B-VII.1	Shift	1.01102 ± 0.00004	Ref.
	Griffin	1.01240	-138

4. REACTIVITY FEEDBACK RESULTS

SEFOR isothermal experiments for cores I-E and I-I were conducted by gradually heating the sodium coolant from approximately 449.8 K to 677.6 K using trace heaters. The total reactivity feedback calculated using the Griffin neutronic models was compared with experimental measurements for both cores, as shown in Figures 5(a) and 5(b). In addition to the experimental data, the Griffin results were benchmarked against the Monte Carlo code, Serpent [7], and ARC models for the same core configurations and test conditions, with the ARC models described in detail in a separate paper dedicated to SEFOR ARC modeling. The Griffin analysis employed axially and radially expanded 3D heterogeneous meshes to reflect the SEFOR temperature distributions and updated MC²-3 multigroup cross sections to account for temperature dependence.

Excellent agreement was observed among the numerical models and with the experimental data, demonstrating the high accuracy of modern reactor physics codes in predicting reactor feedback effects. As summarized in Table 4, for core I-E the numerical models consistently underestimated the total reactivity change by about 3–6% as the core temperature increased from 449.8 K to 677.6 K. The experimental values were taken from Table VIII-1 in Ref. [1] without adjustment. Similarly, Table 5 shows that for core I-I all models, including Serpent, ARC, and Griffin, exhibited comparable discrepancies of less than 3%.

Figure 5. Calculated and measured isothermal reactivity feedback for Core I-E (left) and core I-I (right).

Table 4. Comparison of the calculated total reactivity feedback with experimental value for isothermal tests conducted in core I-E and core temperatures raised from 449.8 K to 677.6 K.

Core I-E		Integral $\Delta\rho$ (cents)	C/E
Measurement*		-253.90	---
Calculation	Nuclear Library	---	---
ARC	ENDF/B-VII.0	-243.6	0.9594
Serpent2	ENDF/B-VII.1	-247.2 ± 3.25	0.9739
	ENDF/B-VIII.0	-247.4 ± 3.26	0.9744
Shift	ENDF/B-VII.0	-238.3 ± 3.63	0.9385
	ENDF/B-VII.1	-240.8 ± 2.76	0.9485
Griffin	ENDF/B-VII.0	-239.6	0.9438
	ENDF/B-VII.1	-239.4	0.9429

* Experimental data obtained from Ref. [1] Table VIII-1.

Table 5. Comparison of the calculated total reactivity feedback with experimental value for isothermal tests conducted in core I-I and core temperatures raised from 449.8 K to 677.6 K.

Core I-I		Integral $\Delta\rho$ (cents)	C/E
Measurement*		-248.8	---
Calculation	Nuclear Library	---	---
ARC	ENDF/B-VII.0	-245.4	0.9864
Serpent2	ENDF/B-VII.1	-243.4 \pm 3.61	0.9784
Griffin	ENDF/B-VII.0	-244.34	0.9821

* Experimental data obtained from Ref. [8] Table 11. Extrapolated from data points at 676.5 K and 677.0 K.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Griffin, a deterministic neutronics code built on MOOSE, was validated against the SEFOR cores I-E and I-I isothermal experiments to assess Doppler and net thermal reactivity feedback. The simulations employed fully heterogeneous 3D meshes from the MOOSE Reactor Module, a DFEM-SN transport solver, and microscopic 33-group MC²-3 cross sections, executed efficiently via a split-mesh, distributed-memory workflow. Griffin’s predictions showed good agreement with SEFOR measurements and with results from Serpent, Shift, and ARC, supporting its accuracy for predicting Doppler and thermal feedback in fast reactors. Future work will extend validation to additional SEFOR configurations and a broader set of experiments, including further isothermal, steady-state, and transient tests, and expanding code-to-code benchmarks to further strengthen confidence in Griffin’s accuracy for fast reactor applications.

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